

ENG SODDA TRIGONOMETRIK TENGLAMALARNI GRAFIK USULDA YECHISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada trigonometric tenglamalarni grafik usulda yechish tushuntirilgan. Ananaviy birlik aylanada yechish usuli maktab kursida tushuntiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Trigonometrik tenglama, yechish, usul, sonlar, javob.

Abstract: This article explains how to solve trigonometric equations graphically. The traditional method of solving the unit circle is explained in the school course.

Key words: Trigonometric equation, solution, method, numbers, answer.

Ma'lumki, maktab kursida trigonometrik tenglamalarni yechish birlik aylanada tushuntiriladi. Trigonometrik tenglamalarni grafik usulda yechish ham sezilarli darajada foyda beradi. Grafik usulda qay tarzda yechish mumkinligi tushuntiramiz.

1. $\cos x = a$ tenglama.

Agar $|a| > 1$, ya'ni $a \in (-\infty; -1) \cup (1; \infty)$ bo'lsa, u holda $\cos x = a$ tenglama yechimga ega emas, chunki har qanday x uchun $|\cos x| \leq 1$.

Endi $|a| \leq 1$, ya'ni $a \in [-1; 1]$ bo'lsin.

Ushbu $\cos x = a$ tenglamani qanoatlantiradigan barcha x larni topaylik.

Faraz qilaylik, $x \in [0; \pi]$ bo'lsin. Ushbu $x \in [0; \pi]$ kesmada yuqorida berilgan tenglamaning bitta aniq yechimi mavjud.

$$x_1 = \arccos a.$$

$y = \cos x$ funksiya –juft funksiya va demak $[-\pi; 0]$ kesmada $\cos x = a$ tenglama yana bitta yechimga ega.

$$x_2 = -\arccos a.$$

Shunday qilib , $\cos x = a$ tenglama $[-\pi; \pi]$ kesmada ikkita yechimga ega :

$$x = \pm \arccos a .$$

$y = \cos x$ funksiyaning davriyligi va uning davri $2\pi n$ bo'lgani sababli qolgan yechimlarning hammasi bu yechimlardan $2\pi n, n \in \mathbb{Z}$ ga farq qiladi .

Ya'ni $\cos x = a, |a| \leq 1$ tenglamaning barcha yechimlari quyidagicha topiladi :

$$x = \pm \arccos a + 2\pi n, n \in \mathbb{Z} , \tag{1}$$

$\cos x = a$ tenglamaning yechimlarini quyidagicha tasvirlash mumkin :

$\cos x = a$ tenglamaning hususiy hollardagi yechimlarini keltiramiz :

1-misol . $\cos x = \frac{1}{2}$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish:

(1) ga ko'ra :

$$x = \pm \arccos \frac{1}{2} + 2\pi n, n \in Z.$$

$\arccos \frac{1}{2} = \frac{\pi}{3}$ bo'lgani uchun ushbu javobga kelamiz:

$$x = \pm \frac{\pi}{3} + 2\pi n, n \in Z.$$

Javob: $x = \pm \frac{\pi}{3} + 2\pi n, n \in Z.$

2-misol . $\cos \left(2x - \frac{\pi}{4} \right) = -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish:

(1) ga ko'ra :

$$2x - \frac{\pi}{4} = \pm \arccos \left(-\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \right) + 2\pi n, n \in Z,$$

$\arccos \left(-\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \right) = \frac{5\pi}{6}$ bo'lgani uchun quyidagini hosil qilamiz:

$$2x = \frac{\pi}{4} \pm \frac{5\pi}{6} + 2\pi n, n \in Z,$$

yoki

$$x = \frac{\pi}{8} \pm \frac{5\pi}{12} + \pi n, n \in Z.$$

Yoki $x_1 = \frac{\pi}{8} + \frac{5\pi}{12} + \pi n = \frac{3\pi + 10\pi}{24} + \pi n = \frac{13\pi}{24} + \pi n, n \in Z$ va

$$x_2 = \frac{\pi}{8} - \frac{5\pi}{12} + \pi n = \frac{3\pi - 10\pi}{24} + \pi n = -\frac{7\pi}{24} + \pi n, n \in Z.$$

Javob: $x = \frac{\pi}{8} \pm \frac{5\pi}{12} + \pi n, n \in Z$

3-misol . $\cos^2 x = 1$ tenglamaning nechta ildizi $x^2 \leq 10$ shartni qanoatlantiradi ?

Yechish:

Dastlab , $x^2 \leq 10$ tengsizlikni yechib olamiz.

$$x^2 - 10 \leq 0 .$$

Chap tomonini ko'paytuvchilarga ajratamiz :

$$(x - \sqrt{10})(x + \sqrt{10}) \leq 0 .$$

Bu tengsizlikni oraliqlar usulida yechib, quyidagi yechimlarni hosil qilamiz:

$$x \in [-\sqrt{10}; \sqrt{10}] .$$

Endi berilgan trigonometrik tenglamani yechamiz.

$$\cos^2 x = 1 .$$

Buning uchun daraja pasaytirish formulasidan foydalanamiz.

$$\frac{1 + \cos 2x}{2} = 1$$

yoki

$$1 + \cos 2x = 2$$

yoki

$$\cos 2x = 1 .$$

Sodda trigonometrik tenglamani yechamiz.

$$2x = 2\pi n, n \in Z$$

yoki

$$x = \pi n, n \in Z .$$

Endi berilgan shartni qanoatlantiradigan yechimlarni topamiz.

$$n = -2 \text{ da } x = -2\pi \approx -2 \cdot 3,14 = -6,28 \notin [-\sqrt{10}; \sqrt{10}] ,$$

$$n = -1 \text{ da } x = -\pi \approx -3,14 \in [-\sqrt{10}; \sqrt{10}] ,$$

$$n=0 \text{ da } x=0 \in [-\sqrt{10}; \sqrt{10}] ,$$

$$n=1 \text{ da } x=\pi \approx 3,14 \in [-\sqrt{10}; \sqrt{10}] ,$$

$$n=2 \text{ da } x=2\pi \approx 2 \cdot 3,14 = 6,28 \notin [-\sqrt{10}; \sqrt{10}] .$$

$n \leq -2$ va $n \geq 2$ larda yechimlar $[-\sqrt{10}; \sqrt{10}]$ kesmaga tegishli bo'lmaydi.

Javob: 3 ta

4-misol . Agar $|\cos x| = 2 + \cos x$ bo'lsa , $2^{\cos x} + 3^{\sin x}$ ning qiymatini toping.

Yechish:

Dastlab , son modulining ta'rifini eslatib o'tamiz. $|a| = \begin{cases} a, \text{ agar } a \geq 0 \text{ bo'lsa} \\ -a, \text{ agar } a < 0 \text{ bo'lsa} \end{cases}$.

$$\text{Demak , } |\cos x| = \begin{cases} \cos x, \text{ agar } \cos x \geq 0 \text{ bo'lsa} \\ -\cos x, \text{ agar } \cos x < 0 \text{ bo'lsa} \end{cases} .$$

1-hol. $\cos x \geq 0$ bo'lsin. U holda

$$\begin{aligned} \cos x &= 2 + \cos x, \\ 0 &= 2 . \end{aligned}$$

Bu holda tenglama yechimga ega emas.

2-hol . $\cos x < 0$ bo'lsin. U holda

$$-\cos x = 2 + \cos x$$

yoki

$$-2 \cos x = 2$$

yoki

$$\cos x = -1.$$

Endi $\sin x$ ning qiymatini topamiz.

$$\sin x = \pm \sqrt{1 - \cos^2 x} = \pm \sqrt{1 - (-1)^2} = \pm \sqrt{1 - 1} = 0 .$$

$$\text{Demak , } 2^{\cos x} + 3^{\sin x} = 2^{-1} + 3^0 = \frac{1}{2} + 1 = \frac{3}{2} = 1,5 .$$

Javob: 1,5.**2. $\sin x = a$ tenglama.**

Xuddi kosinusdagi singari, agar $|a| > 1$, ya'ni $a \in (-\infty; -1) \cup (1; \infty)$ bo'lsa, $\sin x = a$ tenglama ham yechimga ega emas, chunki har qanday x uchun $|\sin x| \leq 1$.

Endi $|a| \leq 1$, ya'ni $a \in [-1; 1]$ bo'lsin.

Ushbu $\sin x = a$ tenglamani qanoatlantiradigan barcha x larni topaylik.

$\left[-\frac{\pi}{2}; \frac{\pi}{2}\right]$ kesmada $\sin x = a$ tenglamaning bitta aniq yechimi bor:

$$x_1 = \arcsin a.$$

$\left[\frac{\pi}{2}; \frac{3\pi}{2}\right]$ kesmada $y = \sin x$ funksiya kamayuvchi va -1 dan 1 gacha hamma qiymatlarni qabul qiladi.

Ildiz haqidagi teorema ko'ra $\sin x = a$ tenglama bu kesmada ham aniq bitta yechimga ega :

$$x_2 = \pi - \arcsin a,$$

$$\sin x_2 = \sin(\pi - x_1) = \sin x_1 = a.$$

Bundan tashqari,

$$-\frac{\pi}{2} \leq x_1 \leq \frac{\pi}{2}$$

bo'lgani uchun va

$$\pi - \frac{\pi}{2} \leq \pi - x_1 \leq \pi + \frac{\pi}{2}$$

ga egamiz, ya'ni x_2 son $\left[\frac{\pi}{2}; \frac{3\pi}{2}\right]$ kesmaga tegishli.

Shunday qilib, $\sin x = a$ tenglama $\left[-\frac{\pi}{2}; \frac{3\pi}{2}\right]$ kesmada ikkita yechimga ega :

$$x_1 = \arcsin a \text{ va } x_2 = \pi - \arcsin a.$$

($a=1$ da bu yechimlar bir xil). Sinusning davriyligini (davri $2\pi n$) hisobga olib, tenglamaning barcha yechimlarini yozish uchun quyidagi formulalarni hosil qilamiz:

$$x = \arcsin a + 2\pi n \tag{*}$$

$$x = \pi - \arcsin a + 2\pi n \tag{**}$$

Ushbu $\sin x = a$ tenglama yechimlarini ikkita emas, balki bitta formula bilan yozish qulay:

$$x = (-1)^k \cdot \arcsin a + \pi k, k \in Z \tag{2}$$

$k = 2n$ larda (2) formuladan (*) formula bilan yozilgan barcha yechimlarni topishga ; $k = 2n + 1$ larda (**) formula bilan yozilgan yechimlarning barchasini topishga oson ishonch hosil qilish mumkin.

$\sin x = a$ tenglamaning yechimlarini quyidagicha tasvirlash mumkin:

$\sin x = a$ tenglamaning hususiy hollardagi yechimlarini keltiramiz:

5-misol. $\sin x = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish: (2) ga asosan: $x = (-1)^k \cdot \arcsin \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} + \pi k, k \in Z$

Tenglamada $\arcsin \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} = \frac{\pi}{4}$ ni almashtiramiz.

$$x = (-1)^k \cdot \frac{\pi}{4} + \pi k, k \in Z.$$

Javob: $x = (-1)^k \cdot \frac{\pi}{4} + \pi k, k \in Z.$

6-misol. $\sin x = 0,3714$ tenglamani taqribiy yeching.

Yechish :

(2) ga asosan

$$x = (-1)^k \cdot \arcsin 0,3714 + \pi k, k \in Z.$$

Kalkulyator yordamida topamiz:

$$\arcsin 0,3714 \approx 0,3805.$$

Berilgan tenglamaning taqribiy yechimi quyidagicha:

$$x \approx (-1)^k \cdot 0,3805 + \pi k, k \in Z.$$

Javob: $x \approx (-1)^k \cdot 0,3805 + \pi k, k \in Z..$

7-misol. $\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{10} - \frac{x}{2}\right) = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish: Sinus – toq funksiya, ya'ni $\sin(-x) = -\sin x$.

Shuning uchun berilgan tenglamani quyidagicha yozamiz:

$$\sin\left(\frac{x}{2} - \frac{\pi}{10}\right) = -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}.$$

(2) ga asosan quyidagini yozamiz:

$$\frac{x}{2} - \frac{\pi}{10} = (-1)^k \arcsin\left(-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\right) + \pi \cdot k, k \in Z,$$

$\arcsin\left(-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\right) = -\frac{\pi}{4}$ bo'lgani uchun:

$$\frac{x}{2} - \frac{\pi}{10} = (-1)^k \left(-\frac{\pi}{4}\right) + \pi \cdot k, k \in Z$$

yoki

$$\frac{x}{2} - \frac{\pi}{10} = (-1)^k \cdot (-1) \cdot \frac{\pi}{4} + \pi \cdot k, k \in Z$$

yoki

$$\frac{x}{2} = \frac{\pi}{10} + (-1)^{k+1} \cdot \frac{\pi}{4} + \pi \cdot k, k \in Z.$$

Tenglamaning ikkala tomonini 2 ga ko'paytiramiz.

$$x = \frac{\pi}{5} + (-1)^{k+1} \cdot \frac{\pi}{2} + 2\pi \cdot k, k \in Z.$$

$$\text{Javob: } x = \frac{\pi}{5} + (-1)^{k+1} \cdot \frac{\pi}{2} + 2\pi \cdot k, k \in Z.$$

8-misol. $|\sin 3x| = \frac{1}{2}$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish: $|f(x)| = a$ tenglama berilgan bo'lsa, uni quyidagicha yozishimiz mumkin:

$$\begin{cases} f(x) = a \\ f(x) = -a \end{cases}$$

Yuqoridagi trigonometrik tenglamani quyidagi ko'rinishda yozamiz:

$$\begin{cases} \sin 3x = \frac{1}{2} \\ \sin 3x = -\frac{1}{2} \end{cases}$$

(2) ga asosan quyidagilarni yozamiz:

$$\begin{cases} 3x = (-1)^k \arcsin \frac{1}{2} + \pi k, k \in Z \\ 3x = (-1)^k \arcsin \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right) + \pi k, k \in Z \end{cases}$$

Ma'lumki, $\arcsin \frac{1}{2} = \frac{\pi}{6}$ va $\arcsin \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right) = -\frac{\pi}{6}$.

$$\begin{cases} 3x = (-1)^k \frac{\pi}{6} + \pi k, k \in Z \\ 3x = (-1)^k \left(-\frac{\pi}{6}\right) + \pi k, k \in Z. \end{cases}$$

Tenglamalarning har birining ikkala tomonini 3 ga bo'lamiz.

$$\begin{cases} x = (-1)^k \frac{\pi}{18} + \frac{\pi k}{3}, k \in Z \\ x = (-1)^{k+1} \frac{\pi}{18} + \frac{\pi k}{3}, k \in Z. \end{cases}$$

Bu ikkala yechimlarni bitta yechim ko'rinishda yozish qulay.

$$x = \pm \frac{\pi}{18} + \frac{\pi k}{3}, k \in Z.$$

$$\text{Javob: } x = \pm \frac{\pi}{18} + \frac{\pi k}{3}, k \in Z.$$

9-misol. $1 - \sin x - \cos 2x = 0$ ($x \in [0; 2\pi]$) tenglamaning ildizlari

yig'indisini toping.

Yechish: Ma'lumki, $\sin^2 x + \cos^2 x = 1$, hamda $\cos 2x = \cos^2 x - \sin^2 x$. Ushbu ayniyatlardan foydalanib, tenglamani quyidagi ko'rinishga keltiramiz:

$$\cos^2 x + \sin^2 x - \sin x - \cos^2 x + \sin^2 x = 0.$$

Soddalashtirgandan so'ng quyidagi tenglikka ega bo'lamiz:

$$2\sin^2 x - \sin x = 0.$$

Qavsdan tashqariga bir xil ko'paytuvchini chiqaramiz :

$$\sin x(2\sin x - 1) = 0.$$

Bu tenglamani yechish uchun har bir ko'paytuvchini 0 ga tenglashtirib yechamiz:

$$1) \sin x = 0, x_1 = \pi k, k \in Z.$$

$$2) 2\sin x - 1 = 0, \sin x = \frac{1}{2}, x_2 = (-1)^k \frac{\pi}{6} + \pi k, k \in Z.$$

Endi $x \in [0; 2\pi]$ bo'lgan yechimlarini topamiz:

$n = -1$ da $x_1 = -\pi$, $x_2 = -\frac{\pi}{6} - \pi$ yechimlar berilgan kesmaga tegishli emas.

$n = 0$ da $x_1 = 0 \in [0; 2\pi]$, $x_2 = \frac{\pi}{6} \in [0; 2\pi]$,

$$n=1 \text{ da } x_1 = \pi \in [0; 2\pi], x_2 = -\frac{\pi}{6} + \pi = \frac{5\pi}{6} \in [0; 2\pi],$$

$$n=2 \text{ da } x_1 = 2\pi \in [0; 2\pi], x_2 = \frac{\pi}{6} + 2\pi = \frac{13\pi}{6} \notin [0; 2\pi].$$

Shunday qilib, tenglamaning berilgan kesmadagi ildizlari yig'indisi quyidagicha:

$$0 + \frac{\pi}{6} + \pi + \frac{5\pi}{6} + 2\pi = 4\pi.$$

Javob: 4π .

10-misol. $8^{\sin^2 x} - 2^{\cos^2 x} = 0$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish: Berilgan tenglamani ko'rsatkichli tenglama deb qarab, bir xil asosga keltiramiz.

$$(2^3)^{\sin^2 x} = 2^{\cos^2 x}$$

yoki

$$2^{3 \cdot \sin^2 x} = 2^{\cos^2 x}.$$

Ma'lumki, $\cos^2 x = 1 - \sin^2 x$. Ushbu ayniyatdan foydalanib, yuqoridagi tenglamani quyidagi ko'rinishda yozib olamiz:

$$2^{3 \cdot \sin^2 x} = 2^{1 - \sin^2 x}.$$

Endi darajalarini tenglashtiramiz:

$$3 \sin^2 x = 1 - \sin^2 x,$$

Tenglamani $\sin^2 x$ ga nisbatan yechamiz.

$$4 \sin^2 x = 1.$$

Tenglamaning ikkala tomonini 4 ga bo'lamiz.

$$\sin^2 x = \frac{1}{4}$$

yoki

$$\sin x = \pm \frac{1}{2}.$$

(2) ga asosan quyidagini yozamiz:

$$\begin{cases} x = (-1)^k \arcsin \frac{1}{2} + \pi \cdot k, k \in Z \\ x = (-1)^k \arcsin \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right) + \pi \cdot k, k \in Z. \end{cases}$$

Ma'lumki, $\arcsin \frac{1}{2} = \frac{\pi}{6}$ va $\arcsin \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right) = -\frac{\pi}{6}$.

$$\begin{cases} x = (-1)^k \frac{\pi}{6} + \pi \cdot k, k \in Z \\ x = (-1)^{k+1} \frac{\pi}{6} + \pi \cdot k, k \in Z. \end{cases}$$

Bu yechimlarni quyidagi bitta tenglik yordamida yozish ham mumkin:

$$x = \pm \frac{\pi}{6} + \pi k, k \in Z.$$

Javob: $x = \pm \frac{\pi}{6} + \pi k, k \in Z.$

3. $tgx = a$ tenglama.

Har qanday a da $\left(-\frac{\pi}{2}; \frac{\pi}{2}\right)$ intervalda aniq bitta shunday x mavjudki,

$tgx = a$ bo'ladi, bu $arctga$ dir. Shu sababli

$$tgx = a$$

tenglama uzunligi π ga teng $\left(-\frac{\pi}{2}; \frac{\pi}{2}\right)$ intervalda aniq bitta ildizga ega.

Tangens - davri π ga teng davriy funksiya bo'lgani uchun tenglamaning qolgan ildizlari topilgan $arctga$ ildizdan $\pi n, n \in Z$ ga farq qiladi, ya'ni

$$x = arctga + \pi n, n \in Z \tag{3}$$

$tgx = a$ tenglamaning yechimlarini quyidagicha tasvirlash mumkin:

11-misol. $tgx = \sqrt{3}$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish: (3) ga ko'ra

$$x = \arctg\sqrt{3} + \pi n, n \in Z,$$

$\arctg\sqrt{3} = \frac{\pi}{3}$ bo'lgani uchun quyidagi

$$x = \frac{\pi}{3} + \pi n, n \in Z$$

yechimlarni keltirib chiqaramiz.

Javob: $x = \frac{\pi}{3} + \pi n, n \in Z$

12-misol. $tgx = 5,177$ tenglamani taqribiy yeching .

Yechish: (3) ga ko'ra

$$x = \arctg 5,177 + \pi n, n \in Z$$

ekani kelib chiqadi.

Kalkulyator yordamida topamiz:

$$\arctg 5,177 \approx 1,3800.$$

Demak ,

$$x \approx 1,38 + \pi n, n \in Z.$$

taqribiy yechimlarni keltirib chiqaramiz.

Javob: $x \approx 1,38 + \pi n, n \in Z.$

13-misol. $ctgx = -\sqrt{3}$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish: Ma'lumki , $ctgx = \frac{1}{tgx}$.

Shuning uchun berilgan tenglamani quyidagi ko'rinishda yozamiz:

$$tgx = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}.$$

(3) ga ko'ra $x = \arctg\left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}\right) + \pi n, n \in Z,$

Tenglamadagi $\arctg\left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}\right) = -\frac{\pi}{6}$ almashtiramiz.

$$x = -\frac{\pi}{6} + \pi n, n \in Z.$$

yechimlarni keltirib chiqaramiz.

Javob: $x = -\frac{\pi}{6} + \pi n, n \in Z.$